

Testing Symmetry with Copula Entropy based Two-Sample Test

Jian Ma*

Hitachi China Research Laboratory

Abstract

We propose a distribution-free method for testing symmetry of distribution with copula entropy based two-sample test. The test statistic is defined as the statistic of two-sample test on symmetric transformation of distribution and its nonparametric estimation method is proposed. Three simulation experiments with beta distribution, asymmetric Laplace distribution, and bimodal normal distribution are conducted to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method and to compare it with the existing methods in the field. Experimental results show that the proposed method measures the symmetry of the simulated distributions effectively and performs best among others.

Keywords: Symmetry Test; Copula Entropy; Two-Sample Test; Distribution Free; Non-Parametric Method

1 Introduction

Symmetry is an important property of probability distribution and symmetry of distribution is an assumption of many statistical models and methods. Tests for it is therefore of very importance in statistics and its various applications. The first such test date back to 18th century by Arbuthnot [1]. There are many existing methods for testing symmetry [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

Two-sample test is to test the hypothesis whether the distributions of two samples are equal. Such tests can be performed by defining test statistic with the measures of statistical independence in two samples, such as kernels base measure [15], mutual information [16]. Two-sample test can be used for testing symmetry, such as [17].

Copula Entropy (CE) is a mathematical concept defined with copula function for measuring statistical independence [18]. Ma and Sun proved that CE is equivalent to mutual information in information theory. They also proposed a nonparametric method for estimating CE [18]. Recently, A two-sample test based on CE was proposed [19], of which the test statistic is defined as the difference between CEs of the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis. This two-sample test was then utilized to solve the change point detection problem

*Email: majian03@gmail.com

recently [20]. CE was also proposed to test multivariate normality, a typical symmetric distribution [21].

In this paper, we propose to test symmetry of distribution with CE based two-sample test. The idea is that: deriving a distribution from the target distribution with symmetry transformation first, and then testing the equality of these two distributions with CE based two-sample test. Since CE based two-sample test is distribution free and universally applicable, so does the symmetry test based it. Another merits of the proposed method is that the test statistic can be estimated non-parametrically.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the related work, Section 3 presents the theory of CE and CE based two-sample test, Section 4 proposes the methods for testing symmetry with CE based two-sample test, simulation experiments with three typical asymmetrical distribution families will be performed in Section 5, followed by discussion in Section 6, and finally Section 7 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

There are several work on testing symmetry with copula function. Bouzebda and Cherfi [22] proposed a test for symmetry with copula function. Kato et al [23] proposed a measure of asymmetry between the lower and upper tail probabilities based on copula function. Mokhtari et al [24] proposed to measure and test conditional asymmetry with copula function. Harder and Stadtmüller [25] proposed to test exchangeability of any dimensional copulas. Bahraoui and Quesy [26] proposed to test exchangeability of multivariate copula based on Lévy measures.

Since copula function itself is also a type of distribution and some of them are asymmetric, there are also work on tests for copula symmetry. For example, Genest et al investigate to test the symmetry of bivariate copula [27, 28]. Erdely and González also proposed a nonparametric symmetry test for bivariate copula [29].

There are also some work on entropy-based symmetry measures. Bormashenko et al proposed a symmetry measure of patterns with information measures [30]. Noughabi and Jarrehiferiz proposed to test symmetry based on entropy of order statistics [31]. Massoumi and Racine proposed to test the symmetry of processes based on entropy [32]. Avhad et al [33] also proposed an entropy-based test for symmetry of distributions.

3 Methodology

3.1 Copula Entropy

Copula theory is about the representation of multivariate dependence with a type of probability function, called copula function [34, 35]. As Sklar's theorem states [36], any multivariate density function can be represented as a copula function with marginal functions as its inputs. The copula functions contain all the information of the dependence between random variables.

Under the blessing of copula theory, Ma and Sun [18] defined a concept for measuring statistical dependence, named Copula Entropy, as follows:

Definition 1 (Copula Entropy). *Let \mathbf{X} be random variables with marginals \mathbf{u} and its associated copula density function $c(\mathbf{u})$. Then the CE of \mathbf{X} is defined as*

$$H_c(\mathbf{x}) = - \int_{\mathbf{u}} c(\mathbf{u}) \log c(\mathbf{u}) d\mathbf{u}. \quad (1)$$

Ma and Sun also proposed a nonparametric method for estimating CE [18], which composed of two simple steps:

1. estimating empirical copula density function $\hat{c}(\mathbf{u})$;
2. estimating the entropy of the estimated empirical copula density $\hat{c}(\mathbf{u})$ as $H_c(\mathbf{X})$.

Empirical copula density $\hat{c}(\mathbf{u})$ in the first step can be easily estimated with rank statistic. After the empirical copula density $\hat{c}(\mathbf{u})$ is estimated, the second step is to estimate the entropy of $\hat{c}(\mathbf{u})$, for which can we propose to use the KSG estimation method [37]. Therefore, a non-parametric method for estimating CE was proposed in [18].

3.2 Two-sample test with CE

CE base two-sample test problem [19] has been proposed recently. Given two samples $\mathbf{X}_1 = \{X_{11}, \dots, X_{1m}\} \sim P_1$, $\mathbf{X}_2 = \{X_{21}, \dots, X_{2n}\} \sim P_2$, the null hypothesis of the proposed two sample test is

$$H_0 : P_1 = P_2, \quad (2)$$

and the alternative hypothesis is

$$H_1 : P_1 \neq P_2. \quad (3)$$

Let $\mathbf{X} = (\mathbf{X}_1, \mathbf{X}_2)$ and Y_0, Y_1 be two labeling variables for the two hypotheses respectively such that $Y_1 = (0_1, \dots, 0_m, 1_1, \dots, 1_n)$ and $Y_0 = (1_1, \dots, 1_{m+n})$. Then one can derive the CEs between \mathbf{X} and Y_i as follows

$$H_c(\mathbf{X}; Y_i) = H_c(\mathbf{X}, Y_i) - H_c(\mathbf{X}). \quad (4)$$

The test statistic is then defined as the difference between the CEs of the two hypotheses as follows:

$$T_{tst}(X_1, X_2) = H_c(\mathbf{X}, Y_0) - H_c(\mathbf{X}, Y_1). \quad (5)$$

T_{tst} is small if H_0 is true and large if H_1 is true. The much different two samples are, the larger T_{tst} is.

The test statistic in (5) can be easily estimated non-parametrically with the non-parametric estimator of CE [19].

4 Method for testing symmetry

Given a sample $X = \{X_i, i = 1, \dots, N\}$ generated from probability density function $p(x) \in R$, u is the mean of x . The problem is to test if p is symmetric with respect to u based on X_i . So the null hypothesis is

$$H_0 : p(u - x) = p(x - u); \quad (6)$$

and the alternative is

$$H_1 : p(u - x) \neq p(x - u). \quad (7)$$

We propose to test symmetry of distribution function p with CE based two-sample test. Let \hat{X} is the sample derived by subtracting the estimated mean \hat{u} from X . Then the problem is transformed into test whether \hat{X} and $-\hat{X}$ are from a same distribution. So the statistic for testing symmetry of p is defined as

$$T_{sym}(X) = T_{tst}(\hat{X}, -\hat{X}). \quad (8)$$

$T_{sym} = 0$ if p is symmetric and $T_{sym} > 0$ if p is asymmetric. The more asymmetric, the larger T_{sym} .

Then the proposed method composed of two simple steps:

1. deriving \hat{X} from X by $\hat{X} = X - \hat{u}$;
2. estimating T_{sym} by performing two-sample test on \hat{X} according to (8).

Since T_{tst} can be estimated non-parametrically, so does T_{sym} .

5 Simulations

5.1 Experiments

In this section we conduct simulation experiments to test the effectiveness of the proposed method and compare it with the existing tests.

Three simulation experiment on different asymmetric distribution families with one parameter for symmetry control are designed. The asymmetric distribution families used in the experiments are:

Beta distribution Beta distribution is a family of continuous probability functions defined on the interval $[0, 1]$ or $(0, 1)$ with two parameters $a, b > 0$ which control the shape of functions, as follows:

$$f(x; a, b) = \frac{\Gamma(a + b)}{\Gamma(a)\Gamma(b)} x^{a-1} (1 - x)^{b-1}, \quad (9)$$

where Γ is the gamma function.

Asymmetric Laplace distribution The asymmetric Laplace distribution is a continuous probability function that generalize the Laplace distribution. It is defined as

$$f(x; \mu, \delta, k) = \frac{1}{\delta(k + k^{-1})} e^{-(x-\mu)k^s s/\delta}, \quad (10)$$

where $s = \text{sgn}(x - \mu)$ and μ, δ are location and scale parameters and k is an asymmetry parameter.

Bimodal normal distribution Bimodal normal distribution is a continuous probability distribution derived by mixing two normal distributions $X_1 \sim N(\mu_1, \delta_1)$ and $X_2 \sim N(\mu_2, \delta_2)$ with a proportion parameter p .

In the simulation with Beta distribution, 9 samples are simulated by letting $a + b = 10$ and $b = 1, \dots, 9$. In the simulation with asymmetric Laplace distribution, 9 samples are simulated with $\mu = 0, \delta = 1$ and $k = 0.1, \dots, 0.9$. In the simulation with bimodal normal distribution, 9 samples are simulated with $\mu_1 = 0, \mu_2 = 5, \delta_1 = \delta_2 = 1$ and $p = 0.1, \dots, 0.9$. The size of all the samples is 300. All the three experiments simulate the distributions changing from asymmetry to symmetry then to asymmetry again.

In the simulations, the R packages `stats`, `ald` and `FamilyRank` are used for simulating Beta distribution, asymmetric Laplace distribution, and bimodal normal distribution respectively.

In the experiments, we compare the proposed method with the existing ones in the field. The R package `copent`[38] is used as the implementation of CE-based two-sample test. The methods implemented in the R package `symmetry` are used for the comparison methods, including:

- MI : The Mira test statistic [9];
- CM : The Cabilio–Masaro test statistic [10];
- MGG : The Miao, Gel and Gastwirth test statistic [6];
- B1 : The $\sqrt{b_1}$ test statistic [8];
- KS : The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test statistic [8];
- SGN : The Sign test statistic [8];
- WCX : The Wilcoxon test statistic [8];
- FM : The characterization based test statistic [11];
- RW : The Rothman-Woodroffe test statistic [12];
- BHI : The Litvinova test statistic [13];
- BHK : The Baringhaus and Henze supremum-type test statistic [4];
- BH2 : The Baringhaus-Henze test statistic [4];
- MOI and MOK : The Milošević and Obradović test statistics [7];
- NAI and NAK : The Nikitin and Ahsanullah test statistics [14];
- K2 and K2U : The Božin, Milošević, Nikitin and Obradović Kolmogorov type statistics based on V- and U- statistics respectively [5];
- NAC1, NAC2, BHC1 and BHC2 : The Allison and Pretorius test statistics [3].

The code for the simulation experiments is available at <https://github.com/majianthu/symmetry>.

5.2 Results

Experimental results with the simulated Beta distribution, asymmetric Laplace distribution, and bimodal normal distribution are shown in Figure 1, 2, and 3 respectively.

It can be learned from the results (Figure 1) of the experiments with Beta distributions that the statistics of the proposed method change from large to almost zero to large again, which means the symmetry of the simulated distributions change from weak to strong and then to weak again. This results measures the symmetry of the simulated distributions correctly. Meanwhile, 4 of the compared methods (BH2, BHC1, NAC1, and NAC2) present similar results while B1, CM, FM, MGG, and MI measure both strength and direction of asymmetry of the simulated distributions.

It can be learned from the results (Figure 2) of the experiments with asymmetric Laplace distribution that the statistics of the proposed method change from large to almost zero to large again which means that the symmetry of the simulated distributions change from weak to strong to weak again, which is the case. Meanwhile, 13 of the compared methods (BH2, BHC1, BHC2, BHK, FM, K2U, K2, KS, MOK, NAC1, NAC2, NAK, and RW) present similar results while B1, BHI, CM, SGN, WCX, MGG, MI, MOI, and NAI measure both strength and direction of the asymmetry of the simulated distributions.

In the simulation results (Figure 3) with bimodal normal distribution, the statistics of the proposed method present two peaks which means the distributions are symmetry at first, middle, and last. These results reflects correctly how the symmetry of the simulated bimodal normal distributions change with p . As contrast, BHC1 and BHC2 present a results with one peak which is close to the situation of the simulated distributions while CM, MGG, and MI measures both strength and direction of the asymmetry of the simulated distribution with one peak and one valley.

6 Discussion

From the simulation results, one can learn that the proposed methods presents more reasonable results than the compared method. In all the three simulation experiments, the proposed method measures the asymmetry of the simulated distributions correctly and only CM, MGG, and MI do similar job. Especially in the simulation with bimodal normal distributions that the distribution is symmetry at middle and close to symmetry at first and last as the proportion of two normal distributions changes by the parameter p , only the statistics of our method and the other three methods (CM, MGG, and MI) measure the symmetry of the simulated distributions correctly.

The proposed test in this paper can be generalized to more cases from different aspects. Here our method only deals with univariate distributions. However, it can be easily generalized to multivariate distributions by testing symmetry in high dimensional spaces. It can also be generalized to test more complicated symmetry since the symmetry considered in this paper is the most basic one. Exchangeability, a special case of distribution symmetry can also be tested with CE based two-sample test in a similar way. Our method considers the symmetry of mean and can be generalized to the cases with the symmetry of median.

Figure 1: Simulation results with Beta distribution.

Figure 2: Simulation results with asymmetric Laplace distribution.

Figure 3: Simulation results with bimodal normal distribution.

7 Conclusions

We propose a method for testing symmetry of distribution with CE based two-sample test. The test statistic is defined as the statistic of two-sample test on symmetric transformation of distributions and its nonparametric estimation method is proposed. Three simulation experiments with beta distribution, asymmetric Laplace distribution, and bimodal normal distribution are conducted to verify the effectiveness of the proposed method and to compare it with the existing methods in the field. Experimental results show that the proposed method can measure the symmetry of the simulated distributions effectively and perform best among others.

References

- [1] John Arbuthnot. Ii. an argument for divine providence, taken from the constant regularity observ'd in the births of both sexes. by dr. john arbuthnott, physitian in ordinary to her majesty, and fellow of the college of physitiens and the royal society. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*, 27(328):186–190, 1710.
- [2] Frank Wilcoxon. Individual comparisons by ranking methods. *Biometrics Bulletin*, 1(6):80–83, 1945.
- [3] James S Allison and Charl Pretorius. A monte carlo evaluation of the performance of two new tests for symmetry. *Computational Statistics*, 32(4):1323–1338, 2017.
- [4] L Baringhaus and N Henze. A characterization of and new consistent tests for symmetry. *Communications in statistics-theory and methods*, 21(6):1555–1566, 1992.
- [5] Vladimir Božin, Bojana Milošević, Ya Yu Nikitin, and Marko Obradović. New characterization-based symmetry tests. *Bulletin of the Malaysian Mathematical Sciences Society*, 43:297–320, 2020.
- [6] Weiwen Miao, Yulia R Gel, and Joseph L Gastwirth. A new test of symmetry about an unknown median. In *Random walk, sequential analysis and related topics: A festschrift in honor of Yuan-Shih Chow*, pages 199–214. World Scientific, 2006.
- [7] Bojana Milošević and Marko Obradović. Characterization based symmetry tests and their asymptotic efficiencies. *Statistics & Probability Letters*, 119:155–162, 2016.
- [8] Bojana Milošević and Marko Obradović. Comparison of efficiencies of some symmetry tests around an unknown centre. *Statistics*, 53(1):43–57, 2019.
- [9] Antonietta Mira and. Distribution-free test for symmetry based on bonferoni's measure. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 26(8):959–972, 1999.
- [10] Paul Cabilio and Joe Masaro. A simple test of symmetry about an unknown median. *The Canadian Journal of Statistics/La Revue Canadienne de Statistique*, 24(3):349–361, 1996.

- [11] Andrey Feuerverger and Roman A Mureika. The empirical characteristic function and its applications. *The Annals of Statistics*, 5(1):88–97, 1977.
- [12] Daniel Gaigall. Rothman–Woodrooffe symmetry test statistic revisited. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 142:106837, 2020.
- [13] VV Litvinova. New nonparametric test for symmetry and its asymptotic efficiency. *Vestnik St. Petersburg University Mathematics*, 34(4):12–14, 2001.
- [14] Ya Yu Nikitin and Mohammad Ahsanullah. New U-empirical tests of symmetry based on extremal order statistics, and their efficiencies. In *Mathematical Statistics and Limit Theorems: Festschrift in Honour of Paul Deheuvels*, pages 231–248. Springer, 2015.
- [15] Arthur Gretton, Karsten M. Borgwardt, Malte J. Rasch, Bernhard Schölkopf, and Alexander Smola. A kernel two-sample test. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 13(25):723–773, 2012.
- [16] Apratim Guha and Tom Chothia. A two sample test based on mutual information. *Calcutta Statistical Association Bulletin*, 66(1-2):39–54, 2014.
- [17] I. H. Tajuddin. Distribution-free test for symmetry based on wilcoxon two-sample test. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 21(5):409–415, 1994.
- [18] Jian Ma and Zengqi Sun. Mutual information is copula entropy. *Tsinghua Science & Technology*, 16(1):51–54, 2011.
- [19] Jian Ma. Two-sample test with copula entropy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.07247*, 2023.
- [20] Jian Ma. Change point detection with copula entropy based two-sample test. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.07892*, 2024.
- [21] Jian Ma. Multivariate normality test with copula entropy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.05956*, 2022.
- [22] Salim Bouzebda and Mohamed Cherfi. Test of symmetry based on copula function. *Journal of Statistical Planning and Inference*, 142(5):1262–1271, 2012.
- [23] Shogo Kato, Toshinao Yoshiba, and Shinto Eguchi. Copula-based measures of asymmetry between the lower and upper tail probabilities. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2008.01314*, 2020.
- [24] E. Mokhtari, A. Dolati, and A. Dastbaravarde. Copula-based measures and tests for conditional asymmetry. *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, 54(1):1–22, 2023.
- [25] Michael Harder and Ulrich Stadtmüller. Testing exchangeability of copulas in arbitrary dimension. *Journal of Nonparametric Statistics*, 29(1):40–60, 2017.
- [26] Tarik Bahraoui and Jean-François Quessy. Tests of multivariate copula exchangeability based on lévy measures. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 49(3):1215–1243, 2022.

- [27] Christian Genest, Johanna Nešlehová, and Jean-François Quessy. Tests of symmetry for bivariate copulas. *Annals of the Institute of Statistical Mathematics*, 64(4):811–834, August 2012.
- [28] Christian Genest and Johanna G. Nešlehová. On tests of radial symmetry for bivariate copulas. *Statistical Papers*, 55(4):1107–1119, November 2014.
- [29] Arturo Erdely and José M. González-Barrios. A nonparametric symmetry test for absolutely continuous bivariate copulas. *Statistical Methods & Applications*, 19(4):541–565, November 2010.
- [30] Edward Bormashenko, Irina Legchenkova, Mark Frenkel, Nir Shvalb, and Shraga Shoval. Informational measure of symmetry vs. Voronoi entropy and continuous measure of entropy of the Penrose tiling. part ii of the “Voronoi entropy vs. continuous measure of symmetry of the Penrose tiling”. *Symmetry*, 13(11), 2021.
- [31] Hadi Alizadeh Noughabi and Jalil Jarrahiferiz. Extropy of order statistics applied to testing symmetry. *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, 51(6):3389–3399, 2022.
- [32] Esfandiar Maasoumi and Jeffrey S. Racine and. A robust entropy-based test of asymmetry for discrete and continuous processes. *Econometric Reviews*, 28(1-3):246–261, 2008.
- [33] Ganesh Vishnu Avhad, Ananya Lahiri, and Sudheesh K. Kattumannil. On testing the class of symmetry using entropy characterization and empirical likelihood approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.08565*, 2025.
- [34] Roger B Nelsen. *An introduction to copulas*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2007.
- [35] Harry Joe. *Dependence modeling with copulas*. CRC press, 2014.
- [36] Abe Sklar. Fonctions de repartition an dimensions et leurs marges. *Publications de l’Institut de statistique de l’Université de Paris*, 8:229–231, 1959.
- [37] Alexander Kraskov, Harald Stögbauer, and Peter Grassberger. Estimating mutual information. *Physical Review E*, 69(6):066138, 2004.
- [38] Jian Ma. copent: Estimating copula entropy and transfer entropy in R. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.14025*, 2021.